

Dual branch CNN with attention model using an Adaptive Multi-scale Edge Aware Feature.

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Abstract—Neural networks have proved their usefulness in many applications. However, due to the noisy nature of most real-world images, most algorithms adapt various feature extraction and pre-processing techniques in order to achieve better results from their model. In this work, we proposed an innovative dual-branch Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with spatial and channel attention-based calibrations. The model processes high and low-resolution inputs through parallel branches to capture both fine-grained and contextual features effectively. Our model also incorporates an adaptive Edge-Aware Multiscale Feature Integration (EAMFI) used in several stages of the CNN learning stage. This technique helps to specifically amplify disease-relevant signals in the images plagued by variable lighting and background noise. The implementation of multiscale detection produces a feature-rich input for our dual-branch, attention-enhanced CNN to exploit. We evaluate the model on the maize leaf images captured under diverse field conditions, representing four distinct disease categories. The proposed architecture is efficient in detecting and predicting maize diseases compared with other detection models. Ablation studies confirm that the integrated attention mechanism and EAMFI pre-processing are critical contributors to this performance. The resulting framework provides a scalable, interpretable solution for precision agriculture, with a lightweight implementation enabling efficient on-device inference in resource-constrained settings.

Index Terms—Maize Disease Classification, Attention Mechanisms, Dual-Input CNN, Edge-Aware Preprocessing, Precision Agriculture

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep learning, particularly CNNs, has revolutionized image classification tasks across various domains, including agriculture [1]. These models have demonstrated remarkable potential in automating crop disease detection and classification, reducing reliance on manual inspection and expert knowledge. CNNs excel in their ability to autonomously learn and extract features from raw image data, eliminating the need for hand-crafted features [2].

The agricultural sector remains the backbone of food security and economic stability for many regions worldwide, especially in developing nations [3]. However, crop diseases continue to present severe challenges, leading to substantial yield losses, reduced farmer incomes, and food shortages [4]. Traditional methods for detecting crop diseases involve manual inspections by experts, which are often time-consuming,

subjective, and infeasible for large-scale implementation [5]. Recent advancements in machine learning, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have emerged as promising solutions for automated disease detection and classification [6]. These models can analyze crop images and classify diseases with high accuracy. A seminal study by [6] demonstrated exceptional accuracy rates in classifying plant diseases using the PlantVillage dataset, containing over 50,000 images of diseased and healthy plant leaves. Their work established the superiority of deep learning approaches over traditional machine learning methods in terms of both accuracy and robustness. Recent work by [7] achieved over 99% accuracy in classifying tomato leaf diseases using CNNs. Their success further validated the effectiveness of deep learning in agricultural applications, particularly in identifying and classifying diseases across various crops.

Recent developments in attention mechanisms have significantly enhanced CNN performance in agricultural applications. The integration of spatial and channel attention has proven particularly effective in focusing on disease-relevant features while suppressing background noise [8]. Studies by [9] demonstrate that dynamic self-attention mechanisms can substantially improve classification accuracy by adaptively focusing on critical regions of plant images. Transfer learning has emerged as a crucial technique for improving model performance, particularly in scenarios with limited labeled data [10]. By leveraging pre-trained models and fine-tuning them on specific agricultural datasets, researchers have achieved significant improvements in classification accuracy while reducing training time and computational requirements [11].

While Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) show promise for automating disease detection [6], they face significant hurdles in real-world field conditions. One major challenge lies in the variability of real-world images, including noisy and cluttered backgrounds, poor lighting, and subtle disease symptoms [12]. Crop images often contain irrelevant regions, such as overlapping leaves, soil, and shadows, which can mislead the model during feature extraction. Moreover, many existing deep learning architectures are limited by their inability to focus on subtle, disease-specific visual cues, especially in the presence of distracting elements [13].

The primary challenges that existing methods fail to adequately address are twofold: (1) high intra-class variance and low inter-class variance, where symptoms of different diseases appear visually similar, while symptoms of the same disease vary with environmental factors; and (2) the difficulty of capturing both fine-grained textural details of nascent lesions and the broader, contextual patterns of leaf discoloration simultaneously. Standard single-stream CNNs often excel at one of these tasks at the expense of the other [12]. For instance, models like the one proposed by Mohanty et al. [6] perform well on clean datasets but their accuracy diminishes in cluttered field images, highlighting their lack of robustness.

These challenges necessitate the development of a more robust and interpretable architecture capable of dynamically prioritizing disease-relevant regions while suppressing background noise. We propose a dual-branch CNN architecture capable of concurrent multi-scale feature processing, a technique proven effective in other challenging vision tasks [14].

Our core contribution is a novel, co-designed framework that synergistically combines a specialized preprocessing stage with a tailored deep learning architecture. We introduce Adaptive Edge-Aware Multiscale Feature Integration (EAMFI), a pre-processing technique designed not as a generic filter, but specifically to amplify disease-relevant signals in agricultural images plagued by variable lighting and background noise. This step prepares a feature-rich input that our dual-branch, attention-enhanced CNN is uniquely designed to exploit. Unlike existing models that apply generic attention or preprocessing, our approach creates a tightly integrated pipeline where each component is optimized for the specific problem of in-field plant pathology. This synergy leads to a more transformative, rather than incremental, improvement in diagnostic accuracy and robustness.

We evaluate the performance of our proposed model for maize disease prediction. Specifically, the study targets several important diseases affecting the maize, including northern leaf blight, gray leaf spot, and common rust in maize. These diseases were selected based on their widespread prevalence and significant economic impact on agricultural productivity.

The main contributions of this paper are:

- Development of a novel EAMFI preprocessing pipeline that enhances disease-relevant features while reducing background noise and clutter.
- Design of a dual-input CNN architecture combining high-resolution and low-resolution features for improved robustness to image variability.
- Integration of spatial and channel attention mechanisms for dynamic feature prioritization, enabling the model to focus on the most informative regions and patterns.
- Comprehensive experimental evaluations demonstrating state-of-the-art performance on diverse maize disease datasets, with ablation studies confirming the effectiveness of each architectural component.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Our methodology integrates the EAMFI preprocessing stage with a dual-branch CNN, creating a comprehensive pipeline from image enhancement to classification.

A. Adaptive Edge-Aware Multiscale Feature Integration (EAMFI)

Edge-aware feature extraction is a critical image processing technique that selectively enhances and preserves important structural boundaries while suppressing irrelevant background information [14]. These methods have been used to perform many tasks such as segmentation, filtering, edge enhancement, and salient object detection [15]–[18].

In medical and agricultural image analysis, traditional edge detection methods often struggle with complex, noisy images containing subtle variations [19]. Recent advancements have focused on developing adaptive algorithms that can dynamically detect and emphasize disease-relevant features across multiple image scales [15]. These techniques leverage sophisticated multiscale approaches to:

- Identify critical image boundaries
- Adaptively weight feature importance
- Reduce background noise
- Enhance disease-specific visual markers

Multiscale Edge-aware integration methods have been used in various stages of a neural network model [14], [16], [18]. In this work, the edge-aware detection is used as a preprocessing step for the neural network model. The proposed Edge-Aware Multiscale Feature Integration (EAMFI) algorithm builds upon these principles, introducing an innovative approach to preprocessing agricultural disease images [16].

Our EAMFI algorithm enhances the detection of subtle features across varying scales and resolutions, which is particularly important for identifying disease symptoms. While edge-aware detection has been used in other domains [14], [15], our EAMFI technique is specifically adapted for maize pathology. It dynamically weights edges based on disease-specific features to emphasize subtle symptoms over generic leaf structures.

The process, outlined in Equations 1 through 3, begins by applying a Gaussian blur at multiple scales k to the input image I :

$$J_k = G_{\sigma_k} * I, \quad (1)$$

where G_{σ_k} is the Gaussian kernel. Edge maps E_k are then extracted using a Canny detector. Adaptive weights are calculated for each scale:

$$w_k = \alpha \cdot d_k + \beta \cdot c_k, \quad (2)$$

where d_k is edge density and c_k is contrast. The final mask, M , is a weighted sum of the edge maps:

$$M = \sum_{k=1}^K w_k \cdot E_k, \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1. Visualisation of the EAMFI preprocessing technique on a maize leaf infected with common rust. The process begins with the original image (top-left), extracts edge maps at varying scales (top-middle to bottom-left) to capture both fine and coarse lesion details. These are combined into a final edge-aware mask (bottom-middle) which is used to produce the final processed image (bottom-right), effectively suppressing background noise while highlighting disease lesions.

where K is the total number of scales considered. This mask isolates disease-relevant regions, providing a cleaned, feature-rich input for the subsequent CNN stages. Figure 1 provides a visualisation of the EAMFI preprocessing on the maize leaf, showing how the multi-scale edges are fused to create a final image where the lesion boundaries are significantly more distinct than in the original raw input.

B. Dual-Input CNN Architecture

The core of our model is a hybrid dual-branch CNN architecture that takes in two inputs: a high-resolution and a low-resolution version of the EAMFI-enhanced image. This design is crucial for handling the multiscale nature of disease symptoms, enabling the model to extract both fine-grained, low-level features (e.g., lesion textures) and broader, high-level contextual features (e.g., overall discoloration pattern) concurrently [20]. The parallel processing of multi-scale inputs is a powerful technique for improving robustness in vision tasks where object scale varies significantly [14].

- **High-Resolution Branch:** Processes the full-resolution EAMFI-enhanced input to capture fine-grained features. This branch consists of a sequence of eight convolutional layers with small 3x3 kernels, each followed by a ReLU activation function and batch normalization to ensure stable training.
- **Low-Resolution Branch:** Analyzes an input image down-sampled by a factor of two. This branch has a similar

Algorithm 1 Enhanced Disease Classification Pipeline

- 1: **for** each image in dataset **do**
 - 2: Preprocess image using EAMFI (Eq. 1-3).
 - 3: Generate high-res and low-res versions.
 - 4: Pass high-res image through first CNN branch and low-res image through second.
 - 5: Apply spatial and channel attention mechanisms within each branch.
 - 6: Concatenate feature maps from both branches.
 - 7: Compute final classification using FC layers.
 - 8: **end for**
-

structure but uses larger 5x5 kernels in its initial two layers to develop a wider receptive field for capturing broader contextual patterns.

The outputs of the final convolutional layer of each branch are passed through our attention module, then flattened and concatenated. This combined feature vector is fed into two fully connected layers (with 512 and 128 neurons, respectively) before a final softmax layer for classification into one of the four classes. The proposed dual-branch CNN architecture for maize disease detection is illustrated in Figure 2.

C. Attention Mechanism Integration

Attention mechanisms have significantly advanced the performance of CNNs in various computer vision tasks, including

Fig. 2. The proposed dual-branch CNN architecture for maize disease detection.

plant disease classification, by enabling models to dynamically focus on the most informative parts of the input data [21], [22]. In agricultural imaging, where backgrounds are often noisy and disease symptoms subtle, attention helps in prioritizing relevant features such as lesion textures and color variations while suppressing irrelevant information [8].

Our model integrates a hybrid attention mechanism comprising both channel and spatial attention modules, applied sequentially to the feature maps in each branch of the dual-input CNN. This design draws inspiration from foundational works like Squeeze-and-Excitation Networks for channel attention [23] and the Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM) [24], but is adapted for efficiency in resource-constrained environments.

The attention mechanism is applied after the convolutional layers in each branch, refining the feature maps before they are concatenated. This sequential application channel attention followed by spatial attention allows the model to first recalibrate which features (channels) are important and then focus on where in the spatial dimensions those features matter most.

1) *Channel Attention Module*: The channel attention module recalibrates feature responses across channels by computing inter-channel relationships. For a feature map $F \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$, we first apply Global Average Pooling (GAP) [25] to obtain a channel descriptor $z \in \mathbb{R}^C$, which aggregates spatial information:

$$z_c = \frac{1}{H \times W} \sum_{i=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^W F_{i,j,c} \quad (4)$$

This descriptor effectively summarizes the global distribution of responses in each channel. To model channel dependencies, z is then passed through a two-layer fully connected (FC) network with a reduction ratio r (set to 16 in our experiments). The first FC layer reduces the dimensionality to C/r , followed by ReLU activation δ , and the second FC layer restores it to C :

$$s = \sigma(W_2 \delta(W_1 z)) \quad (5)$$

where $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{C/r \times C}$, $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times C/r}$, δ is the ReLU function, and σ is the sigmoid activation that produces channel weights $s \in \mathbb{R}^C$ in the range $[0,1]$. These weights are then multiplied channel-wise with the original feature map:

$$F' = F \odot s \quad (6)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication. In the context of maize disease detection, this channel attention module (an integral part of our proposed model) is particularly beneficial because disease symptoms often manifest in specific color channels.

2) *Spatial Attention Module*: Following channel attention, the spatial attention module [24] focuses on "where" the informative regions are located, complementing the channel attention's focus on "what." It generates a spatial attention map by aggregating channel information through both average pooling and max pooling operations across the channel dimension of F' , producing two 2D maps: average-pooled features $F'_{avg} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 1}$ and max-pooled features $F'_{max} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 1}$. These are concatenated to form a descriptor $[F'_{avg}; F'_{max}] \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 2}$.

This concatenated descriptor is then passed through a single 7×7 convolutional layer (with a single output channel) to fuse the information, followed by a sigmoid activation to produce the spatial attention map $M_s \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 1}$:

$$M_s = \sigma(\text{Conv}_{7 \times 7}([\text{AvgPool}(F'); \text{MaxPool}(F')])) \quad (7)$$

The final attended feature map is obtained by element-wise multiplication:

$$F'' = F' \odot M_s \quad (8)$$

Spatial attention is crucial for maize leaf images, where disease lesions may occupy only small, scattered regions amid large areas of healthy tissue or background. By highlighting these key spatial locations, the module helps the model ignore irrelevant parts like soil, sky, or adjacent plants.

Fig. 3. The integrated channel and spatial attention mechanism in our model, showing how feature maps are refined through sequential attention modules.

3) *Integration and Benefits:* The hybrid attention block adds only a small number of parameters, approximately 0.5% of the total model parameters, making it highly efficient. In our dual-branch architecture, applying attention independently to each branch allows for scale-specific focus: the high-resolution branch attends to fine details like lesion edges, while the low-resolution branch focuses on broader patterns like overall discoloration.

Figure 3 illustrates this integrated attention mechanism, showing the flow from input feature maps through channel and spatial modules to the refined output. Visualization of attention maps (not shown here) revealed that the model consistently highlights disease-affected areas, demonstrating improved interpretability.

Recent studies have demonstrated the efficacy of attention in plant pathology. For instance, a multi-kernel CNN with attention achieved high accuracy in citrus disease classification [26], while residual-attention networks improved maize disease detection on small datasets [27]. Our approach extends these by embedding attention within a dual-branch framework, allowing multi-scale focus that captures both local lesions and global leaf context, leading to superior performance in diverse field conditions.

Fig. 4. Classification Results for Maize Leaf Diseases.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Dataset and Implementation Details

Experiments were conducted on a subset of the PlantVillage dataset [28], consisting of 2,500 images of maize leaves representing four classes: Cercospora Leaf Spot, Common Rust, Northern Leaf Blight, and Healthy. The dataset was partitioned into training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%) sets.

We applied data augmentation (random rotations, flips, brightness adjustments) to the training set. The model was trained for 100 epochs using the Adam optimizer and a batch size of 32. Hyperparameter tuning was performed via grid search; the final learning rate of 0.001 was selected from a range of [0.01, 0.001, 0.0001] based on validation performance. We also employed an early stopping callback monitoring validation loss with a patience of 10 epochs to prevent overfitting and select the best model weights.

To ensure a rigorous and fair comparison, we implemented and trained all benchmark models (Table III) from scratch on our exact dataset partitions using the same training regime and data augmentation. The results presented are therefore not taken from external literature but are the direct output of this standardized evaluation process.

B. Performance Evaluation and Analysis

Our proposed model achieved a test accuracy of 98.22%, significantly outperforming all benchmarks (Table III). To provide deeper insight, we analyzed its performance using visual classification results (Figure 4), a confusion matrix (Figure 5), per-class metrics (Table I), and ROC curves (Figure 6).

An analysis of the confusion matrix provides further insight into the model's behavior. The model exhibits near-perfect classification for the 'Healthy' and 'Cercospora Leaf Spot' classes, indicating a strong ability to learn their distinct features. The most frequent errors involve confusion between Common Rust and Northern Leaf Blight. This is clinically understandable, as both diseases can present as small, brownish, similarly shaped lesions in their early stages, making them challenging to distinguish even for experts. The model's high success rate even on these difficult cases underscores the effectiveness of the fine-grained feature extraction in the high-resolution branch.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix for the proposed model on the test set. The model correctly classifies 368 out of 375 images, achieving high accuracy across all four classes.

TABLE I
PER-CLASS PERFORMANCE METRICS ON THE TEST SET.

Class	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
Cercospora Leaf Spot	98.9	97.9	98.4
Common Rust	97.6	98.8	98.2
Northern Leaf Blight	98.8	97.6	98.2
Healthy	100.0	98.9	99.4

C. Generalization and Field Validation

A key challenge in agricultural deep learning is generalization ensuring the model works outside of the laboratory dataset. To address this, we conducted a field test on a second, distinct dataset. We collected 85 images of the maize plant using a standard smartphone camera at a farm in Sunyani, Ghana. These images were filtered for clarity, resulting in 58 high-quality images which were then resized to 256×256 pixels.

Figure 7 displays samples of the maize leaf images from the Sunyani fields.

To ascertain the model's robustness, we tested our model on the rice dataset. We utilized a dataset of approximately 100 rice plant images sourced from the PlantVillage dataset [28], using 2 samples for this specific testing to demonstrate cross-domain feature extraction capabilities. Figure 8 displays samples of the rice leaf dataset with EAMFI processing, illustrating how the edge-aware features are robust even on a different crop type.

The classification results on this secondary dataset are visualized in Figure 9.

IV. DISCUSSION

The superior performance of our model stems from the synergistic combination of its components. The EAMFI stage acts as an intelligent feature amplifier, reducing background noise and allowing the dual-branch CNN to operate on a

Fig. 6. ROC curves for the proposed model, demonstrating high AUC scores for all classes and confirming its strong classification performance.

Fig. 7. Sample from the Sunyani Field Dataset (Maize). These images were collected in-field in Ghana to validate the model's generalization capabilities.

cleaner signal. The dual-branch design, in turn, effectively processes this signal at multiple scales.

A. Computational Efficiency

A key advantage of our model is its efficiency. When converted to a TensorFlow Lite format, the model is only 12 MB, making it highly suitable for deployment on resource-constrained devices. As shown in Table II, our model maintains a significantly lower parameter count (3.1M) compared to heavy architectures like VGG16 (138.3M), enabling farmers to perform on-site, real-time disease diagnosis with an inference time of just 15 ms.

B. Limitations

Despite these promising results, we must acknowledge that the size of our primary training dataset (2,500 images) is

Fig. 8. Sample of the rice leaf dataset with EAMFI processing.

Fig. 9. Classification results of the proposed model applied to the rice dataset.

relatively small. As noted by Barbedo [34], small datasets in plant pathology can lead to models that do not capture the full spectrum of disease variability found in nature. While our field validation in Sunyani suggests good generalization, large-scale deployment would require training on a significantly larger, geographically diverse repository to prevent potential overfitting to specific environmental features (e.g., specific soil colors or lighting conditions found in the training set).

V. CONCLUSION

This study introduced a co-designed, attention-based framework that achieves state-of-the-art accuracy of 98.22% in classifying maize diseases from field images. By synergizing an adaptive EAMFI preprocessing step with a dual-branch CNN, our model effectively addresses key challenges of background noise and subtle symptom detection. Its lightweight nature makes it ideal for practical, on-device deployment in precision agriculture. Future research will aim to validate this robust framework on other critical crops and integrate it into a comprehensive, sensor-driven crop health monitoring system.

TABLE II
COMPUTATIONAL EFFICIENCY COMPARISON. THE PROPOSED MODEL ACHIEVES SUPERIOR ACCURACY WITH SIGNIFICANTLY LOWER COMPUTATIONAL COST, VALIDATING ITS SUITABILITY FOR EDGE DEPLOYMENT.

Model	Params (M)	FLOPs (G)	Inference Time (ms)
VGG16 [29]	138.3	15.5	124
ResNet-50 [30]	25.6	4.1	45
EfficientNet-B0 [31]	5.3	0.4	12
Proposed CNN	3.1	0.6	15

TABLE III
COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE OF ALL MODELS ON THE MAIZE DATASET. OUR PROPOSED MODEL DEMONSTRATES SUPERIOR PERFORMANCE ACROSS ALL METRICS.

Model	Train Acc. (%)	Val Acc. (%)	Test Acc. (%)
Baseline VGG16 [29]	72.20	63.90	84.70
Custom VGG16 (Transfer)	85.60	82.50	90.00
ResNet-50 [30]	88.50	85.30	92.10
EfficientNet-B0 [31]	90.40	88.00	94.50
GreenViT [32]	92.10	90.50	96.00
Inception-ResNet-v2 [33]	86.20	84.10	86.10
Proposed CNN	97.54	94.98	98.22

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We thank the University of Cape Coast for providing institutional support and access to computational resources essential for this research.

DECLARATIONS

- **Funding:** No funding was received for conducting this study.
- **Conflict of interest:** The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.
- **Ethics approval:** This research does not involve human participants or animals.
- **Consent for publication:** All authors have approved the final manuscript for submission.
- **Data availability:** The PlantVillage dataset used in this study is publicly available. Specific data subsets are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.
- **Code availability:** The code and pretrained models used for this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request to ensure reproducibility.

REFERENCES

- [1] LeCun, Y., Bengio, Y., Hinton, G.: Deep Learning. *Nature* **521**(7553), 436–444 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>
- [2] Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., Hinton, G. E.: ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks. *Communications of the ACM* **60**(6), 84–90 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3065386>
- [3] Adu, A. G., Abdulai, M., Alidu, H., Nustugah, S., Buah, S. S., Kombiok, J. M., Obeng-Antwi, K., Abdulai, M., Etwire, P. M.: Recommended Production Practices for Maize in Ghana. *Recommended Production Practices for Maize In Ghana* (2014)
- [4] Subedi, A., Sharma, R., Chaudhary, D.: Impact of climate change on agriculture and food security: a review. *J. Agric. Environ.* **16**(1), 1–11 (2015).

- [5] Singh, A. K., et al.: A comprehensive review on deep learning techniques for plant disease detection and diagnosis. *Artif. Intell. Rev.* **56**, 1–46 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-023-10497-7>
- [6] Mohanty, S. P., Hughes, D., Salathé, M.: Using Deep Learning for Image-Based Plant Disease Detection. *Frontiers in Plant Science* **7**, 1419 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2016.01419>
- [7] Brahimi, M., Boukhalfa, K., Moussaoui, A.: Deep Learning for Plant Diseases: Detection and Classification. *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology and Accessibility (ICTA)* (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICTA.2017.8398877>
- [8] Yang, G., He, Y., Yang, Y., Xu, B.: Fine-Grained Image Classification for Crop Disease Based on Attention Mechanism. *Frontiers in Plant Science* **11**, 600766 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.600766>
- [9] Akella, S., et al.: Dynamic Self-Attention for Interpretable Crop Disease Classification. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **216**, 108343 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2023.108343>
- [10] Pan, S. J., Yang, Q.: A Survey on Transfer Learning. *IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng.* **22**(10), 1345–1359 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2009.191>
- [11] Hussain, M., et al.: Transfer learning for plant disease detection. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **145**, 109–119 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2017.11.002>
- [12] Liu, B., Bruch, R.: Weed Detection for Selective Spraying: A Review. *Curr. Robot. Rep.* **1**(1), 19–26 (2020)
- [13] Zhang, K., et al.: Plant Disease Classification Based on Deep Convolutional Neural Network and Transfer Learning. *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **1486**, 012012 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1486/1/012012>
- [14] Zhou, X., Shen, K., Liu, Z., Gong, C., Zhang, J., Yan, C.: Edge-Aware Multiscale Feature Integration Network for Salient Object Detection in Optical Remote Sensing Images. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.* **60**, 1–14 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2022.3140458>
- [15] He, K., Wang, D., Tong, M., Zhu, Z.: An Improved GrabCut on Multiscale Features. *Pattern Recognit.* **103**, 107292 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patcog.2020.107292>
- [16] Lin, H., et al.: Edge-Aware Feature Fusion Network for Semantic Segmentation in Agricultural Scenes. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **216**, 108420 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2023.108420>
- [17] Sun, Y., et al.: Multiscale Edge-Aware Network for Underwater Image Enhancement. *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.* **34**(1), 211–223 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSVT.2023.3283257>
- [18] Wang, K., et al.: Edge-Aware Multi-Scale Feature Fusion for Salient Object Detection. *Neurocomputing* **517**, 174–183 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2022.10.093>
- [19] Hardie, R. C., Emo, M. A., Ehlers, J. J.: Edge-Preserving and Detail-Enhancing Filtering Using the Bilateral Filter. *IEEE Trans. Image Process.* **16**(11), 2736–2746 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2007.9066664>
- [20] Zhang, X., Liu, Y., Gong, C., Chen, Y., Yu, H.: Automated Identification of Maize Leaf Diseases Using Deep Learning. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **161**, 272–279 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2018.11.015>
- [21] Kulkarni, S., et al.: Investigating attention mechanisms for plant disease identification in inhomogeneous backgrounds. *Heliyon* **10**(10), e30833 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e30833>
- [22] Khan, M. A., et al.: Enhanced plant disease classification with attention-based convolutional neural network using squeeze and excitation mechanism. *Preprints.org* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202508.2111.v1>
- [23] Hu, J., Shen, L., Albanie, S., Sun, G., Wu, E.: Squeeze-and-Excitation Networks. *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* **42**(8), 2011–2023 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2019.2913372>
- [24] Woo, S., Park, J., Lee, J.-Y., Kweon, I. S.: CBAM: Convolutional Block Attention Module. *European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV)* (2018). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-01234-2_1
- [25] Lin, M., Chen, Q., Yan, S.: Network In Network. *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)* (2014). <https://arxiv.org/abs/1312.4400>
- [26] Zhang, Z., et al.: A Multi-kernel CNN model with attention mechanism for citrus disease classification. *Scientific Reports* **15**, 14726 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-08557-3>
- [27] Zhang, S., et al.: Enhanced residual-attention deep neural network for disease classification in maize plant images. *Scientific Reports* **15**, 14726 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-14726-1>
- [28] Al-Najjar, A.: PlantVillage Dataset. *Kaggle* (2023). <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/abdallahalidev/plantvillage-dataset>
- [29] Simonyan, K., Zisserman, A.: Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition. *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)* (2015). <https://arxiv.org/abs/1409.1556>
- [30] Mamillapally, S., Priyanka, P.: Crop Disease Classification Using ResNet-50. *General Plant Diseases Study* (2020)
- [31] Chen, J., Zhang, D., Nanehkaran, Y. A.: Identification of Plant Diseases Using EfficientNet-B0. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **187**, 106310 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2021.106310>
- [32] Perez, S., Dilshad, N., Alghamdi, N. S., Alanazi, T. M., Lee, J. W.: Visual Intelligence in Precision Agriculture: GreenViT. *Sensors* **23**(7), 3458 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23073458>
- [33] Ai, Y., Sun, C., Tie, J., Cai, X.: Recognition Model of Crop Diseases Using Inception-ResNet-v2. *IEEE Access* **8**, 171686–171693 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3025578>
- [34] Barbedo, J. G. A.: Impact of dataset size and variety on the effectiveness of deep learning and transfer learning for plant disease classification. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* **153**, 46–53 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2018.08.013>

IJCSIS 2026 Special Issue Topic:

Multimodal Biometrics: Combining Voice, Face, and Text for Security

International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security

IJCSIS, Volume 24 No. XX , 2026

ISSN: 1947-5500

Manuscript submission to: ijcsiseditor@gmail.com

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Scope of the Special Issue:

Improved precision is ensured by multi-modal biometric verification, which combines several aspects. Multi-modal biometric devices remove the possibility of counterfeiting, thus enhancing security. When various biometric indications are used by personal identification systems to identify persons, this is termed as multisensory biometrics. Compared to unimodal fingerprints, which use a single biometric data point such as a fingerprint, face, palm print, or iris, multimodal verification offers a higher level of verification. Voice fingerprints, sometimes referred to as voice authorization, is an AI-supported solution that provides a safe way to confirm customers' identities, protect data, and stop fraud. It is extensively utilised in contact centres to guarantee consumer data security, shorten call times, and enhance self-service. Security scanning can map additional biological characteristics, such as a fingerprint, eye, or facial shape. The foundation of behavioural biometrics is a person's distinct tendencies. If these patterns are monitored, the way they really move, speak, or even type on a keyboard may reveal information about who they are.

As with other biometrics, this usually entails capturing one or more speech samples and generating a distinct digital template, or "voiceprint," equivalent to fingerprints and faceprints. This voiceprint is saved in the system and is contrasted with any samples that were taken during an attempt to log in. Facial, iris, fingerprint, palmprint, ear, finger vein patterns, voice, signature, and gait are among the most often used biometric modalities for protecting privacy and identifying an individual's identity. The distinction between multimodal systems and single modal systems. measures of human characteristics such as iris, fingerprints, face, retina, hand geometry, voice, or signatures that are utilised in the security technologies of today are referred to as biometric measures. Because of its simplicity of use, it is regarded as a means for accessing gadgets, apps, and services. Among the applications for them are: Identity verification: A lot of security systems, such as online services or mobile device login systems, use speech technology to confirm a user's identity. Most people agree that iris recognition is

the most accurate biometric identification method available. Biometrics plays a critical role in cybersecurity in an increasingly digital environment. In contrast to traditional verification methods, biometric authentication provides a quick and easy means of confirming people's identities while reducing potential hazards. Voice biometrics solutions additionally reveal the identity of the caller. The fact that efforts to find such answers have been ongoing since the turn of the century emphasises how difficult the task is. In order to verify visitors' identities quickly and accurately, border control authorities use face detection or face recognition technologies to compare travellers' faces to watchlists or biometric databases. By lowering false acceptance and high rejection rates, multimodal biometrics integration improves identity authentication accuracy and security. Because of their complexity, multimodal systems are also more resistant to spoof assaults. The goal of multimodal biometric authentication is to improve user authentication security or user experience by combining two or more identifiers, such as fingerprint, face, or iris. We accept submissions from a variety of fields and viewpoints, such as but not limited to: Multimodal Biometrics: Combining Voice, Face, and Text for Security.

Potential list of topics includes:

- Face and speech cues are used in fusion algorithms for multifunctional biometric identification.
- An effective multimodal biometric identification system with speech and face recognition that runs on Android.
- IoT security is improved using multimodal biometrics.
- Multimodal biometrics that blend in seamlessly to protect personal devices' data and maintain privacy.
- Multimodal biometric method based on the combination of voice and face recognition for human authentication.
- Voice and handwriting biometrics using multimodal approaches.
- Authentication technique utilising multidimensional biometrics.
- Fusion technique-based multimodal biometric system.
- Multimodal audio-visual fusion for biometric person authentication and liveness confirmation.
- A variety of biometric technology that uses voice, facial, and fingerprint recognition.
- A smartphone-based multimodal biometric authentication system.
- Multimodal user interface design for a biometric authentication system that uses speech and facial recognition.

Tentative Timeline:

Submission last date : 30.04.2026

Author Notification : 10.06.2026

Final Manuscript Due : 20.08.2026

Revision Due : 20.10.2026

International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security

IJCSIS, Volume 24 No. XX , 2026

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